

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHINAY RAJESH** bearing USN **2SU21AC001** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“EXPECTED RETURNS IN FINANCE AND ACCOUNTING”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AFZAL ALI** bearing USN **2SU21AC002** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“EXPECTED RETURNS IN FINANCE AND ACCOUNTING”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALBI VARGHESE** bearing USN **2SU21AC003** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“EXPECTED RETURNS IN FINANCE AND ACCOUNTING”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANJANA C V** bearing USN **2SU21AC004** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“EXPECTED RETURNS IN FINANCE AND ACCOUNTING”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ARCHANA ASHOK** bearing USN **2SU21AC005** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“EXPECTED RETURNS IN FINANCE AND ACCOUNTING”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ARJUN VIJAY** bearing USN **2SU21AC006** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“EXPECTED RETURNS IN FINANCE AND ACCOUNTING”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DISHA L N** bearing USN **2SU21AC007** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“EXPECTED RETURNS IN FINANCE AND ACCOUNTING”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FAYEZA MAIMUNA** bearing USN **2SU21AC008** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“EXPECTED RETURNS IN FINANCE AND ACCOUNTING”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **G NAZAF AHMED** bearing USN **2SU21AC009** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“EXPECTED RETURNS IN FINANCE AND ACCOUNTING”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ISHAL BIRDIA CRASTA** bearing USN **2SU21AC010** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“EXPECTED RETURNS IN FINANCE AND ACCOUNTING”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KARTHIK S** bearing USN **2SU21AC011** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“EXPECTED RETURNS IN FINANCE AND ACCOUNTING”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KAVITHA M** bearing USN **2SU21AC012** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“STUDYING THE BENEFITS OF BUSINESS ACCOUNTING CONCERNING MODERN TECHNOLOGY”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KRISHNA NAYAK KALYANPUR** bearing USN **2SU21AC013** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“STUDYING THE BENEFITS OF BUSINESS ACCOUNTING CONCERNING MODERN TECHNOLOGY”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms LARAIB ZAFAR bearing USN 2SU21AC014 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “STUDYING THE BENEFITS OF BUSINESS ACCOUNTING CONCERNING MODERN TECHNOLOGY” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MACLYN MERWIN PASHAO** bearing USN **2SU21AC015** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“STUDYING THE BENEFITS OF BUSINESS ACCOUNTING CONCERNING MODERN TECHNOLOGY”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED IRSHAD SAYEED** bearing USN **2SU21AC016** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“STUDYING THE BENEFITS OF BUSINESS ACCOUNTING CONCERNING MODERN TECHNOLOGY”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED NAIF** bearing USN **2SU21AC017** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“STUDYING THE BENEFITS OF BUSINESS ACCOUNTING CONCERNING MODERN TECHNOLOGY”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED NIHAL M S** bearing USN **2SU21AC018** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“STUDYING THE BENEFITS OF BUSINESS ACCOUNTING CONCERNING MODERN TECHNOLOGY”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED RIJAS P P bearing USN 2SU21AC019 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “STUDYING THE BENEFITS OF BUSINESS ACCOUNTING CONCERNING MODERN TECHNOLOGY” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NANDAN P bearing USN 2SU21AC020 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “STUDYING THE BENEFITS OF BUSINESS ACCOUNTING CONCERNING MODERN TECHNOLOGY” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIHAL K P bearing USN 2SU21AC021 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “STUDYING THE BENEFITS OF BUSINESS ACCOUNTING CONCERNING MODERN TECHNOLOGY” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **POOJARY SHREYA VITTAL** bearing USN **2SU21AC022** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ROLE OF MODERN ACCOUNTING IN THE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF EMERGING ECONOMIES”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAFAD ABDULLAKUTTY bearing USN **2SU21AC023** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ROLE OF MODERN ACCOUNTING IN THE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF EMERGING ECONOMIES”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year **2021-22.****

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAINAL SHYNA FERNANDES** bearing USN **2SU21AC024** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ROLE OF MODERN ACCOUNTING IN THE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF EMERGING ECONOMIES”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAFINA S** bearing USN **2SU21AC025** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ROLE OF MODERN ACCOUNTING IN THE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF EMERGING ECONOMIES”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHAMVIL MANEGAR bearing USN 2SU21AC026 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “ROLE OF MODERN ACCOUNTING IN THE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF EMERGING ECONOMIES” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHEES AHAMED** bearing USN **2SU21AC027** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ROLE OF MODERN ACCOUNTING IN THE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF EMERGING ECONOMIES”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year **2021-22**.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHILNA V V** bearing USN **2SU21AC028** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ROLE OF MODERN ACCOUNTING IN THE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF EMERGING ECONOMIES”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year **2021-22**.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHRAMITHA S** bearing USN **2SU21AC029** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ROLE OF MODERN ACCOUNTING IN THE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF EMERGING ECONOMIES”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year **2021-22**.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREERAG B K** bearing USN **2SU21AC030** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ROLE OF MODERN ACCOUNTING IN THE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF EMERGING ECONOMIES”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year **2021-22**.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUHAIB V A** bearing USN **2SU21AC031** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ROLE OF MODERN ACCOUNTING IN THE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF EMERGING ECONOMIES”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year **2021-22**.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SYED MOHAMMED AKIF bearing USN 2SU21AC032 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “ROLE OF MODERN ACCOUNTING IN THE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF EMERGING ECONOMIES” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ZUHAIR MUHAMMED** bearing USN **2SU21AC033** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ROLE OF MODERN ACCOUNTING IN THE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF EMERGING ECONOMIES”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year **2021-22**.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL BASITH bearing USN **2SU21HS001** has completed his/her minor project on the topic “**EFFECTS OF ACCOUNTING INFORMATION ON COST OF CAPITAL OF A FIRM**” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL ROUF SAIFAL bearing USN **2SU21HS002** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“EFFECTS OF ACCOUNTING INFORMATION ON COST OF CAPITAL OF A FIRM”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABOUBAKAR ARMAN** bearing USN **2SU21HS003** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“EFFECTS OF ACCOUNTING INFORMATION ON COST OF CAPITAL OF A FIRM”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABOUBAKER SHEHZIR** bearing USN **2SU21HS004** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“EFFECTS OF ACCOUNTING INFORMATION ON COST OF CAPITAL OF A FIRM”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AFHAM AHMED** bearing USN **2SU21HS005** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“EFFECTS OF ACCOUNTING INFORMATION ON COST OF CAPITAL OF A FIRM”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AFIF IQBAL HEGGARNI bearing USN 2SU21HS006 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “EFFECTS OF ACCOUNTING INFORMATION ON COST OF CAPITAL OF A FIRM” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHMED ARMAN** bearing USN **2SU21HS007** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“EFFECTS OF ACCOUNTING INFORMATION ON COST OF CAPITAL OF A FIRM”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AJMAL SHUHAIID.B** bearing USN **2SU21HS008** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“EFFECTS OF ACCOUNTING INFORMATION ON COST OF CAPITAL OF A FIRM”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
College of Management and Commerce
www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in
deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms *AMZAR AKRAM* bearing USN *2SU21HS009* has completed his/her minor project on the topic “*A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE SCOPE OF TOTAL INCOME AND RESIDENTIAL STATUS*” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean
College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
College of Management and Commerce
www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in
deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANANDU ANIL bearing USN 2SU21HS010 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE SCOPE OF TOTAL INCOME AND RESIDENTIAL STATUS” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean
College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANUSHREE** bearing USN **2SU21HS011** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE SCOPE OF TOTAL INCOME AND RESIDENTIAL STATUS”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AVANTHIKA HARI C bearing USN 2SU21HS012 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE SCOPE OF TOTAL INCOME AND RESIDENTIAL STATUS” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj'.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms B M SAYYED SHAHIL bearing USN 2SU21HS013 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE SCOPE OF TOTAL INCOME AND RESIDENTIAL STATUS” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms BEERAN AMEER ALI bearing USN 2SU21HS014 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE SCOPE OF TOTAL INCOME AND RESIDENTIAL STATUS” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
College of Management and Commerce
www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in
deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms HASSAN SAHIL bearing USN 2SU21HS015 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE SCOPE OF TOTAL INCOME AND RESIDENTIAL STATUS” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read "Keerthan Raj", is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean
College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **IBRAHIM SAIF ALI** bearing USN **2SU21HS016** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE SCOPE OF TOTAL INCOME AND RESIDENTIAL STATUS”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JAGADEESHA B bearing USN 2SU21HS017 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE SCOPE OF TOTAL INCOME AND RESIDENTIAL STATUS” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms KAVAN B N bearing USN 2SU21HS018 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE SCOPE OF TOTAL INCOME AND RESIDENTIAL STATUS” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
College of Management and Commerce
www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in
deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KISHANDEV K** bearing USN **2SU21HS019** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“HIGHLIGHT THE FUNDAMENTAL PRINCIPLES RELATING TAX LAWS”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean
College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KRUTHIK S** bearing USN **2SU21HS020** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“HIGHLIGHT THE FUNDAMENTAL PRINCIPLES RELATING TAX LAWS”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SA.AD P B** bearing USN **2SU21HS021** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“HIGHLIGHT THE FUNDAMENTAL PRINCIPLES RELATING TAX LAWS”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, consisting of stylized, cursive letters, is positioned above the name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
College of Management and Commerce
www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in
deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AFAN** bearing USN **2SU21HS022** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“HIGHLIGHT THE FUNDAMENTAL PRINCIPLES RELATING TAX LAWS”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean
College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
College of Management and Commerce
www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in
deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED ARAFATH bearing USN 2SU21HS023 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “HIGHLIGHT THE FUNDAMENTAL PRINCIPLES RELATING TAX LAWS” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean
College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
College of Management and Commerce
www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in
deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED AYYUB bearing USN 2SU21HS024 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “HIGHLIGHT THE FUNDAMENTAL PRINCIPLES RELATING TAX LAWS” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean
College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
College of Management and Commerce
www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in
deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AZMATH** bearing USN **2SU21HS025** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“HIGHLIGHT THE FUNDAMENTAL PRINCIPLES RELATING TAX LAWS”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, consisting of several loops and a long horizontal stroke, is positioned above the name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean
College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FARAZ** bearing USN **2SU21HS026** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“HIGHLIGHT THE FUNDAMENTAL PRINCIPLES RELATING TAX LAWS”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
College of Management and Commerce
www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in
deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED HARSHAD bearing USN 2SU21HS027 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “HIGHLIGHT THE FUNDAMENTAL PRINCIPLES RELATING TAX LAWS” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, consisting of a series of loops and strokes, is positioned above the name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean
College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ISMAIL ASLAH** bearing USN **2SU21HS028** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“HIGHLIGHT THE FUNDAMENTAL PRINCIPLES RELATING TAX LAWS”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MOOSA HASHIR** bearing USN **2SU21HS029** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“CRITICALLY EVALUATE THE TAXING POWER AND CONSTITUTIONAL LIMITATION”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED RAAID YOUNUS SHAIKH bearing USN 2SU21HS030 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “CRITICALLY EVALUATE THE TAXING POWER AND CONSTITUTIONAL LIMITATION” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED SINAN C H bearing USN 2SU21HS031 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “CRITICALLY EVALUATE THE TAXING POWER AND CONSTITUTIONAL LIMITATION” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MONISHA. A bearing USN **2SU21HS032** has completed his/her minor project on the topic “**CRITICALLY EVALUATE THE TAXING POWER AND CONSTITUTIONAL LIMITATION**” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NAJEEB MEHFOOS K.P** bearing USN **2SU21HS033** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“CRITICALLY EVALUATE THE TAXING POWER AND CONSTITUTIONAL LIMITATION”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
College of Management and Commerce
www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in
deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PREETHA** bearing USN **2SU21HS034** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“CRITICALLY EVALUATE THE TAXING POWER AND CONSTITUTIONAL LIMITATION”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean
College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **R ASHWINI** bearing USN **2SU21HS035** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“CRITICALLY EVALUATE THE TAXING POWER AND CONSTITUTIONAL LIMITATION”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj'.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RACHANA** bearing USN **2SU21HS036** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“CRITICALLY EVALUATE THE TAXING POWER AND CONSTITUTIONAL LIMITATION”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj'.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAQIB WARITH** bearing USN **2SU21HS037** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“CRITICALLY EVALUATE THE TAXING POWER AND CONSTITUTIONAL LIMITATION”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **S K MOHAMMED FAHEEQ HUSSAIN** bearing USN **2SU21HS038** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“CRITICALLY EVALUATE THE TAXING POWER AND CONSTITUTIONAL LIMITATION”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj'.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAYED AFWAN bearing USN **2SU21HS039** has completed his/her minor project on the topic “**A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE INCOME FROM HOUSE PROPERTY**” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHHAZ AHMED** bearing USN **2SU21HS040** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE INCOME FROM HOUSE PROPERTY”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHREJAL** bearing USN **2SU21HS041** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE INCOME FROM HOUSE PROPERTY”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
College of Management and Commerce
www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in
deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SNEHA KASHINATH GALKAR** bearing USN **2SU21HS042** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE INCOME FROM HOUSE PROPERTY”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean
College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
College of Management and Commerce
www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in
deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SONI DKHAR bearing USN 2SU21HS043 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE INCOME FROM HOUSE PROPERTY” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean
College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **USMAN JASIR B M** bearing USN **2SU21HS044** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE INCOME FROM HOUSE PROPERTY”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VARSHA** bearing USN **2SU21HS045** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE INCOME FROM HOUSE PROPERTY”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **WILCITA LOBO** bearing USN **2SU21HS046** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE INCOME FROM HOUSE PROPERTY”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL NOUSHEEF** bearing USN **2SU21HS047** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE INCOME FROM HOUSE PROPERTY”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL RAHIMAN AFIL bearing USN **2SU21CM001** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF DEDUCTION OF TAX AT SOURCE AND ADVANCE TAX”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL RAHMAN ASIM** bearing USN **2SU21CM002** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF DEDUCTION OF TAX AT SOURCE AND ADVANCE TAX”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK K** bearing USN **2SU21CM003** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF DEDUCTION OF TAX AT SOURCE AND ADVANCE TAX”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
College of Management and Commerce
www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in
deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AHMED NASIM SINAN bearing USN 2SU21CM004 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF DEDUCTION OF TAX AT SOURCE AND ADVANCE TAX” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean
College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKHIL P M bearing USN **2SU21CM005** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF DEDUCTION OF TAX AT SOURCE AND ADVANCE TAX”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANISH KUMAR bearing USN 2SU21CM006 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF DEDUCTION OF TAX AT SOURCE AND ADVANCE TAX” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANUSREE K P bearing USN 2SU21CM007 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF DEDUCTION OF TAX AT SOURCE AND ADVANCE TAX” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ARJUN A** bearing USN **2SU21CM008** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF DEDUCTION OF TAX AT SOURCE AND ADVANCE TAX”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
College of Management and Commerce
www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in
deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASNA M** bearing USN **2SU21CM009** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF DEDUCTION OF TAX AT SOURCE AND ADVANCE TAX”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean
College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ATHUL KRISHNA U A bearing USN **2SU21CM010** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF DEDUCTION OF TAX AT SOURCE AND ADVANCE TAX”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

A handwritten signature in green ink, consisting of a series of fluid, connected loops and strokes, positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AVISHEK BHATTARAI** bearing USN **2SU21CM011** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF DEDUCTION OF TAX AT SOURCE AND ADVANCE TAX”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHARLIE SARASWATI** bearing USN **2SU21CM012** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A STUDY ON THE DEDUCTIONS UNDER CHAPTER – VI OF THE INCOME TAX ACT, 1961”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
College of Management and Commerce
www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in
deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DEEKSHA P** bearing USN **2SU21CM013** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A STUDY ON THE DEDUCTIONS UNDER CHAPTER – VI OF THE INCOME TAX ACT, 1962”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean
College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DELCIA LOBO bearing USN 2SU21CM014 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “A STUDY ON THE DEDUCTIONS UNDER CHAPTER – VI OF THE INCOME TAX ACT, 1963” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DHANIK S GOWDA bearing USN **2SU21CM015** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A STUDY ON THE DEDUCTIONS UNDER CHAPTER – VI OF THE INCOME TAX ACT, 1964”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DHANYA K D** bearing USN **2SU21CM016** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A STUDY ON THE DEDUCTIONS UNDER CHAPTER – VI OF THE INCOME TAX ACT, 1965”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HAJIM MOHAMAD BATISH** bearing USN **2SU21CM017** has completed his/her minor project on the topic “**A STUDY ON THE DEDUCTIONS UNDER CHAPTER – VI OF THE INCOME TAX ACT, 1966**” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj'.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
College of Management and Commerce
www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in
deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms HARASHATH KUMAR P S bearing USN 2SU21CM018 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “A STUDY ON THE DEDUCTIONS UNDER CHAPTER – VI OF THE INCOME TAX ACT, 1967” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean
College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
College of Management and Commerce
www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in
deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms HASAN ARSHIQ bearing USN 2SU21CM019 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “A STUDY ON THE DEDUCTIONS UNDER CHAPTER – VI OF THE INCOME TAX ACT, 1968” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean
College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
College of Management and Commerce
www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in
deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JABIR C K bearing USN **2SU21CM020** has completed his/her minor project on the topic “**A STUDY ON THE DEDUCTIONS UNDER CHAPTER – VI OF THE INCOME TAX ACT, 1969**” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean
College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
College of Management and Commerce
www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in
deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms LERINA DSOUZA bearing USN 2SU21CM021 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “A STUDY ON THE DEDUCTIONS UNDER CHAPTER – VI OF THE INCOME TAX ACT, 1970” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean
College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms LIKHITH BHANDARY bearing USN 2SU21CM022 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “A STUDY ON THE TAXABLE WEALTH, DETERMINATION OF ASSETS AND WEALTH TAX AUTHORITIES” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms LISHA VIOLA D'SOUZA bearing USN 2SU21CM023 has completed his/her minor project on the topic "A STUDY ON THE TAXABLE WEALTH, DETERMINATION OF ASSETS AND WEALTH TAX AUTHORITIES" in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MAHMAD SHAMEER H A bearing USN 2SU21CM024 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “A STUDY ON THE TAXABLE WEALTH, DETERMINATION OF ASSETS AND WEALTH TAX AUTHORITIES” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MARIAM SAFRINA bearing USN **2SU21CM025** has completed his/her minor project on the topic “**A STUDY ON THE TAXABLE WEALTH, DETERMINATION OF ASSETS AND WEALTH TAX AUTHORITIES**” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MITHILA.P. NAIR** bearing USN **2SU21CM026** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A STUDY ON THE TAXABLE WEALTH, DETERMINATION OF ASSETS AND WEALTH TAX AUTHORITIES”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMAD ALFAZ** bearing USN **2SU21CM027** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A STUDY ON THE TAXABLE WEALTH, DETERMINATION OF ASSETS AND WEALTH TAX AUTHORITIES”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj'.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED ANISH bearing USN 2SU21CM028 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “A STUDY ON THE TAXABLE WEALTH, DETERMINATION OF ASSETS AND WEALTH TAX AUTHORITIES” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED RABEEH M bearing USN 2SU21CM029 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “A STUDY ON THE TAXABLE WEALTH, DETERMINATION OF ASSETS AND WEALTH TAX AUTHORITIES” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED RAZIK K bearing USN 2SU21CM030 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “A STUDY ON THE TAXABLE WEALTH, DETERMINATION OF ASSETS AND WEALTH TAX AUTHORITIES” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED RIFATH R bearing USN **2SU21CM031** has completed his/her minor project on the topic “**A STUDY ON THE TAXABLE WEALTH, DETERMINATION OF ASSETS AND WEALTH TAX AUTHORITIES**” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SHANOON RAHIMAN** bearing USN **2SU21CM032** has completed his/her minor project on the topic “**A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF DEDUCTION OF TAX AT SOURCE AND ADVANCE TAX**” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMAD SINAN bearing USN 2SU21CM033 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF DEDUCTION OF TAX AT SOURCE AND ADVANCE TAX” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED MUFEEED A M** bearing USN **2SU21CM034** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF DEDUCTION OF TAX AT SOURCE AND ADVANCE TAX”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED RIZWAN M bearing USN 2SU21CM035 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF DEDUCTION OF TAX AT SOURCE AND ADVANCE TAX” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED SAVAD bearing USN **2SU21CM036** has completed his/her minor project on the topic “**A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF DEDUCTION OF TAX AT SOURCE AND ADVANCE TAX**” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRADEEP NEOPANE** bearing USN **2SU21CM037** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF DEDUCTION OF TAX AT SOURCE AND ADVANCE TAX”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRANAMYA B** bearing USN **2SU21CM038** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF DEDUCTION OF TAX AT SOURCE AND ADVANCE TAX”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
College of Management and Commerce
www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in
deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SADHAN K S bearing USN 2SU21CM039 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF DEDUCTION OF TAX AT SOURCE AND ADVANCE TAX” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean
College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SARAMATH JASEENA bearing USN 2SU21CM040 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF DEDUCTION OF TAX AT SOURCE AND ADVANCE TAX” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAYYAD AFRID** bearing USN **2SU21CM041** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF DEDUCTION OF TAX AT SOURCE AND ADVANCE TAX”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAHZAN SHAZULI K A bearing USN **2SU21CM042** has completed his/her minor project on the topic “**CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF VAT SYSTEM IN INDIA**” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHIMNA K** bearing USN **2SU21CM043** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF VAT SYSTEM IN INDIA”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, consisting of several fluid, connected strokes, is positioned above the name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHWETHA** bearing USN **2SU21CM044** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF VAT SYSTEM IN INDIA”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, consisting of several loops and a long horizontal stroke, is positioned above the name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **TOM JOSE** bearing USN **2SU21CM045** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF VAT SYSTEM IN INDIA”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **TUSHAR BHARADHWAJ PAI** bearing USN **2SU21CM046** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF VAT SYSTEM IN INDIA”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **UBAIDULLAH ASLAM** bearing USN **2SU21CM047** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF VAT SYSTEM IN INDIA”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VAISHAK S** bearing USN **2SU21CM048** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF VAT SYSTEM IN INDIA”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VAISHALI** bearing USN **2SU21CM049** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF VAT SYSTEM IN INDIA”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VANDANA** bearing USN **2SU21CM050** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF VAT SYSTEM IN INDIA”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj'.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VASISTA KAIPANGALA** bearing USN **2SU21CM051** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF VAT SYSTEM IN INDIA”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, consisting of several fluid, connected strokes, is positioned above the name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
College of Management and Commerce
www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in
deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VASUDESHA** bearing USN **2SU21CM052** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF VAT SYSTEM IN INDIA”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean
College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms VISHAL VISHWAKARMA bearing USN 2SU21CM053 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF VAT SYSTEM IN INDIA” in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
College of Management and Commerce
www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in
deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **YOGANANDA B S** bearing USN **2SU21CM054** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF VAT SYSTEM IN INDIA”** in the First year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean
College of Management and Commerce